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A Study on Awareness of Narcotics Among Young-Adult Students

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ABSTRACT

In this prospective and longitudinal study on “A study on awareness of narcotics among young adult students” the awareness programs are conducted among young adult students aged from 18-25 years, where the chances of incidence of narcotics misuse is high. The study objectify to evaluate the effectiveness of current educational programs and awareness campaigns on narcotic addiction prevention among young-adult students. Study also explore the attitudes and beliefs of young-adult students towards narcotic addiction and related risks and identify the knowledge gaps and misconceptions regarding the risks and consequences of narcotic addiction among young-adult students. This prospective quantitative study focuses on young-adult students in a community setting. Inclusion criteria encompass all genders willing to participate, excluding children, the elderly, and those with mental or neurological disorders unwilling to engage. The study employs a questionnaire-based approach across multiple colleges, utilizing pre and post-questionnaires with an intervening narcotic awareness presentation. Statistical analysis using SPSS version 23.0 involves percentages, proportions, means, medians, and the Chi-square test to evaluate the relationship between independent variables and key outcomes (knowledge, attitude, and awareness related to narcotics). A p-value of 0.05 is considered statistically significant. The study focused on gender distribution among young adults, with a higher male ratio (65.1%) indicating an elevated risk of narcotics introduction. Primarily targeting students, the awareness program involved college faculties and staff. Examining age distribution, the highest awareness was in the 22-23 age group, emphasizing the need for targeted educational efforts. Duration of stay in Bangalore was considered for lifestyle assessment, given its potential impact on narcotics misuse. Pre-program awareness was low at 7.6%, but post-program, 97.7% were well-informed, with significant increases in knowledge about risk, addiction, and signs/symptoms. Confidence in information about narcotics saw a positive change, with 93.4% feeling more confident post-program. Participants believed their colleges lacked adequate narcotics information (89.6%), reflecting a potential institutional gap..

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Attitudes shifted positively, with concerns decreasing from 90.9% to 85.4%. Peer pressure was identified as a significant cause, and confidence in resisting increased from 93% to 85%. The study highlighted barriers to prevention, including education, stigma, and peer pressure. Participants expressed concerns about insufficient resources for those struggling with narcotics (89.5%). The majority believed that increasing awareness and education could prevent future narcotics addiction cases (98.2%). Suggestions included more awareness campaigns and support groups/resources for young adults struggling with narcotics. While 92.7% attended narcotics addiction awareness programs for the first time, a considerable percentage had not participated in any peer support group, yet recognized the potential effectiveness of such programs (91.9%). The findings underscore the importance of targeted educational interventions and institutional support to address narcotics-related challenges among young adults. In conclusion, the study underscores the positive impact of awareness programs on knowledge and attitudes, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and ongoing support in combating narcotics misuse among young adults.

INTRODUCTION

Narcotics, a diverse group of substances known for their potent effects on pain relief and consciousness alteration, have held a significant yet controversial role throughout human history. From their ancient use as remedies for ailments to their contemporary association with addiction and abuse, narcotics represent a dual-edged phenomenon. This document explores the multifaceted nature of narcotics, highlighting their historical, cultural, and medicinal significance while addressing the complex challenges they present in modern society. While narcotics are invaluable in managing severe pain and improving quality of life for patients, their potential for misuse and dependency has led to widespread physical, psychological, and societal harm. The focus of this study is particularly on young adults, a demographic at heightened risk due to factors such as peer pressure, social experimentation, academic and personal stress, and increased accessibility to both prescription and illicit narcotics. The document examines the underlying drivers of narcotic misuse in this group, including

inadequate awareness of the risks, insufficient education on addiction, and the influence of social and cultural norms. It also addresses the alarming trends in addiction rates, overdose incidents, and the role of synthetic narcotics like fentanyl in exacerbating the global drug crisis. Furthermore, the study evaluates existing strategies for prevention, awareness, and harm reduction, identifying significant gaps in educational campaigns and intervention efforts. Current approaches are analyzed for their effectiveness in equipping young adults with the knowledge and resilience needed to navigate the risks associated with narcotics. Harm-reduction measures, such as supervised injection sites, naloxone distribution, and broader access to addiction treatment, are explored as potential solutions to mitigate the impact of narcotics misuse on individuals and society. The broader implications of the narcotics crisis are also considered, including its effects on public health systems, law enforcement, and communities. The global illicit drug trade, fueled by demand for narcotics, is examined for its role in perpetuating violence, economic instability, and societal disintegration. The study emphasizes the need for international cooperation and evidence-based policymaking to combat these challenges effectively. Through this in-depth exploration, the document aims to illuminate the intricate and often paradoxical role of narcotics in human society. By examining their historical context, current challenges, and the impact on young adults, the study advocates for a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach to addressing the narcotics crisis. It calls for informed policy interventions, enhanced education programs, and robust community support systems to mitigate the harmful effects of narcotics while preserving their legitimate medical use. Ultimately, this work aspires to contribute to a future where the balance between the therapeutic benefits and societal risks of narcotics is more effectively managed,

safeguarding the well-being of individuals and communities alike.

RESULTS

The results of the study highlight a significant increase in awareness and knowledge about narcotics among young adults following an educational program. Before the intervention, only 7.6% of participants were aware of what narcotics are, but this increased dramatically to 97.7% post-program. Similarly, understanding the risks associated with narcotics rose from 8.2% to 97.9%. Awareness of addiction as a critical issue improved substantially, with the percentage of students recognizing addiction as a significant problem rising from 9.6% to 98.1%. Confidence in knowledge about narcotics saw a remarkable increase, with 93.4% of participants feeling more informed post-program compared to just 6.4% beforehand. Additionally, 85% of participants reported greater confidence in resisting peer pressure after the program, compared to only 1% before. Concerns about the current opioid epidemic rose from 4.1% to 92.7%, reflecting heightened awareness. Barriers to addressing

narcotics misuse were identified, with lack of education (43.3%), peer pressure (40%), and stigma (16.7%) as primary obstacles. A significant majority (96.9%) of participants expressed a need for more awareness campaigns, while 96.6% believed in the necessity of more support groups and resources for young adults dealing with narcotics issues. These findings underscore the effectiveness of educational interventions in transforming awareness and attitudes toward narcotics among young adults. They also highlight critical gaps in existing resources and the need for sustained efforts in awareness, education, and community support to address narcotics-related challenges comprehensively.

Result: -

Demographics

Table no. 01: Distribution of subjects according to gender

Gender	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Female	624	34.9%
Male	335	65.1%
Total	959	100%

Figure no. 01

Subjects were being distributed according to gender. In the total identified population, the female gender number 335 (34.9%) and male

gender 624 (65.1%). Here the reason of greater ratio in male population is because of their more chances to introduce towards narcotics.

Table no. 02: Distribution according to age group

Age	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
18-19	138	14.4%
20-21	331	34.5%
22-23	383	39.9%

24-25	107	11.2%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=476.34 df=13 p value, sig=0.011, significant

Figure no. 02

From the distribution of subjects according to age, a greater number of population were aware at the age group of 22 to 23 (39.9%) and 20 to 21 (34.5%), and the least were found in the age group of 18 to 19 years (11.2%) and then 24 to 25 years (14.4%).

The study only focus students how ever while conducting an awareness programme college faculties and other staffs were also involved in the programme. The reason of mainly focusing the students in this study is because of their lifestyle which increase the chances of substance misuse.

Table no. 03: Distribution according to stay in Bangalore

Years	Frequency In Number (959)	Percentage (%)
>1 year	156	16.3%
1-2 years	296	30.9%
2-4 years	302	31.6%
<4 years	203	21.2%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=332.43 df=04 p value, sig=0.013, significant

Figure no. 04

As the study conduct in the Bangalore it was important to understand their staying period in Bangalore which helps in the assessment of their lifestyle changes in various factor such as freedom, new friend circle etc. Which again can lead to the narcotics misuse.

Knowledge

Table no. 04: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Are You Aware of What Narcotics Are?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
Yes	73 (92.4%)	937 (97.7%)
No	886 (7.6%)	22 (2.3%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=819.44 df=08 p value, sig=0.0115, significant

Figure no. 05

Out of the 959 young adults only 73 (i.e 7.6%) were aware of “what narcotics are” before the awareness program. After the program a assessment with a post questionnaire has been done, where a significant change has been seen. Sample 937 (i.e 97.7%) out of 959 young adult has been well informed and aware about the narcotics.

Table no. 05: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Know the Risks Associated with Using Narcotics?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
Yes	79 (8.2%)	939 (97.9%)
No	880 (91.8%)	20 (2.1%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=674.429 df=03 p value, sig=0.0134, significant

Most of the young adults were not aware of the “risk associated with using narcotics” before the program i.e 880(91.8%) out of total 959. The significant change has been seen after the program almost 939 i.e 97.9% of the total young adults were well informed about the risk and consequences associated with narcotics.

Table no. 06: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Think Addictions Are a Significant Issue Among Young-Adult Students?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
Yes	92 (9.6%)	941 (98.1%)
No	867 (90.4%)	18 (1.9%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=1331.78 df=09 p value, sig=0.0211, significant

Before the program most of the young adults (i.e 867 out of 959) were not aware about the narcotics addiction and its significant issue. After the program a significant change in knowledge has been seen where 941 (i.e 98.1%) students understand the depth of the addiction of the narcotics.

Table no. 07: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Know Signs and Symptoms of a Narcotic Overdose?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
Yes	877 (91.4%)	941 (98.1%)
No	82 (8.6%)	18 (1.9%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=573.51 df=11 p value, sig=0.0125, significant

χ^2 value=19.444 df=20 p value, sig=0.493, NS (Not significant)

The students were not aware about the sign and symptoms of narcotics before the program i.e 877(91.4%) out of 959 people were not clearly known about the sign and symptoms of narcotics. After the program the significant change in knowledge about the sign and symptoms has been seen, i.e 941 (98.1%) young adults out of the total 959 sample were well informed about the sign and symptoms of the narcotics.

Table no. 08: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

How Informative Are You About Narcotics?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
More	62 (6.4%)	896 (93.4%)
Less	881 (91.9%)	33 (3.44%)
Intermediate	16 (1.66%)	30 (3.12%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=781.98 df=13 p value, sig=0.0311, significant

Figure no. 09

The sample young adult were not confident with the information that they have about narcotics. Out of 959 young adult only 62(i.e 6.4%) were well informative about the narcotics and other 881 (i.e 91.9%) were not well informative about the narcotics. After the awareness program a significant change in knowledge about information of narcotics has been seen, app 896 population i.e 93.4% young adult were feel more confident about the information of narcotics.

Do You Feel That Your College or University Provides Adequate Education and Resources on Narcotics?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	859	(89.6%)
No	100	(10.4%)
Total	959	(100%)

χ^2 value=724.234 df=14 p value, sig=0.0225, significant

Table no. 09: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Figure no. 10

The current education program were not supply the required needed information about narcotics in their colleges or universities. Almost 859 out of 959, i.e 89.6% young adult student believe that their colleges and universities do not provide the adequate information about the narcotics.

Table no. 10: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

How Would You Rate Your	Pre-Question	Post-Question
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Knowledge About Narcotic Addictions on A Scale Of 1 To 10?		
1-4	759 (82.9%)	56 (5.83%)
4-7	143 (14.9%)	51 (5.3%)
7-10	21 (2.1%)	852 (88.8%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

Figure no. 11

The knowledge of narcotics among young adults, before the program were significantly less, 759 out of 959 i.e 82.9% students' rate 'less' about the information they have about the narcotics. After the program a significant change in knowledge and confidence about narcotics information has been observed, 852 out of 959 i.e 88.8% students' rate more about the knowledge of narcotics after the program.

Attitude

Table no. 11: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

How Concerned Are You About the Potential Risks and Consequences of Using Narcotic Substances?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
Slightly Concerned	872 (90.9%)	59 (6.1%)
Moderately Concerned	76 (7.9%)	81 (8.4%)
Very Concerned	11 (1.2%)	819 (85.4%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=782.34 df=16 p value, sig=0.0345, significant

Table no. 12: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

The attitude of young adults were not strongly concern about the potential risk and consequences of using narcotics, 872 out of 959 i.e 90.9% students believe that they are slightly concern about the risks of narcotics before the program. Where a significant change has been seen after the awareness program and 819 out of 959 i.e 85.4% students were concerned about the risk and consequences of using narcotics, and their attitude and knowledge about narcotics after the program looks improve.

To What Extent Do You Believe That Narcotic Addiction Is a Serious Problem Among Young-Adult Students in Our Community?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
A Minor Problem	889 (92.7%)	61 (6.3%)
Somewhat Of A Problem	55 (5.7%)	73 (7.6%)
A Major Problem	15(1.5%)	825 (86%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=1374.234 df=14 p value, sig=0.0127, significant

Before the program, 889 out of 959 young adult students i.e 92.7% believe that the narcotics problem in our community is a minor problem, this is because of the lack of information and unawareness of the current problem of narcotics addiction. After the program the students were well informed about the narcotics and a significant change in their attitude has been seen and 825 out of 959 students were believe that the problem of narcotics is a major problem in our community.

Table no. 13: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

How Confident Do You Feel in Your Ability to Resist Peer Pressure to Use Narcotic Substances?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
Slightly Confident	892 (93%)	57 (5.9%)
Moderately Confident	58 (6%)	87 (9.1%)
Very Confident	09 (1%)	815 (85%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=982.34 df=12 p value, sig=0.0138, significant

Peer pressure is a major cause to introduce the narcotic misuse in young adult students. Before the program 892 out of 959 i.e 93% students were not confident or slightly confident to resist the peer pressure where after the program a significant change in the attitude to resist the peer pressure has been seen, 815 out of 959 i.e 85% students were very confident to resist the peer pressure to use narcotics after the program.

Awareness

Table no. 14: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Know Where to Go for Help If You or Someone You Know Is Struggling with A Narcotic Addiction?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
Yes	59 (6.2%)	928 (96.8%)
No	900 (93.8%)	31 (3.2%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=898.34 df=11 p value, sig=0.009, significant

The students were not aware about “where to ask for help if someone is struggling with narcotics”, about 900 out of 959 i.e 93.8% young adults were not knew about where to ask help if someone is struggling with narcotics before the program. After the program, a significant change in awareness has been seen and 928 out of 959 i.e 96.8% students were well informed about where to ask help if someone is struggling with narcotics.

Table no. 15: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

How Concerned Are You About the Current Opioid Epidemic?	Pre-Question	Post-Question
More	40 (4.1%)	889 (92.7%)
Less	903 (94.2%)	47 (4.9%)
Intermediate	16 (1.6%)	23 (2.3%)
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=1237.34 df=15 p value, sig=0.01, significant

Figure no. 16

Current opioid crisis is a disaster to the community but most of the students were not concern about the current opioid epidemic, before the program 903 out of 959 i.e 94.2% students were not concern about the current opioid epidemic. but after the program a significant change in the awareness of current epidemic has been seen where 889 out of 959 i.e 92.7% young adults were well concern about the current opioid epidemics.

Table no. 16: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Have You Ever Received Education or Training on Narcotics and Its Consequences?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	40	7.1%
No	903	92.9%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=1263.43 df=09 p value, sig=0.0113, significant

Figure no. 17

Most of the young adults were attending the narcotics education program for the first time in their life. 903 out of 959 i.e 92.9% students were not attend or received any kind of education or training program on narcotics and its consequences.

Table no. 17: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

What Do You Think Are the Biggest Barriers to Awareness	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Lack Of Education	415	43.3%
Stigma Surroundings	116	16.7%
Peer Pressure	384	40%
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

and Prevention of Narcotic Addiction Among Young-Adult Students?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Lack Of Education	415	43.3%
Stigma Surroundings	116	16.7%
Peer Pressure	384	40%
Total	959(100%)	959(100%)

χ^2 value=1373.763 df=07 p value, sig=0.041, significant

Young adult is the phase of life where many challenges need to be face by the students and there could be various reasons comes as a barrier for prevention of narcotics misuse. In our assessment of total 959 young adults, 415 i.e 43.3% students believe that the barriers could be because of lack of education, 116 i.e 16.7% students believe the barrier could be because of unhealthy stigma surroundings, and 384 i.e 40% students believe that the barriers could be because of peer pressure.

Table no. 18: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Think There Are Enough Resources Available for Those Struggling with Narcotic Addictions?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	101	10.5%
No	858	89.5%
Total	959	100%

Figure no. 19

There are very limited resources available for those who struggling with narcotics. Out of 959 students 858 i.e 89.5% young adult believe that

there are not enough resources available for those who struggling with narcotics.

Table no. 19: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Think Increased Awareness and Education About Narcotic Addictions Could Help Prevent Future Cases of Addiction?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	942	98.2%
No	17	1.8%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=873.74 df=12 p value, sig=0.002, significant

Figure no. 20

Awareness and education is always the best way to deal with any kind of addiction. 942 i.e 98.2% young adult out of 959 students believe that increasing awareness and education about narcotics could help prevent future cases of narcotics addiction.

Table no. 20: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Think There Should Be More Awareness Campaigns Focused on Narcotic Addictions in Young-Adult Populations?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	929	96.9%
No	30	3.1%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=938.767 df=15 p value, sig=0.007, significant

Figure no. 21

Most of the sample population in our study were attending awareness program regarding narcotics for the first time in their life. 929 i.e 96.9% students out of total 959 young adults think there

should be more awareness campaigns who are focused on narcotics addiction among young adult students.

Table no. 21: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Do You Think There Should Be More Support Groups or Resources Specifically for Young-Adult Students Struggling with Narcotic Addictions?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	926	96.6%
No	33	3.4%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=893.67 df=11 p value, sig=0.007, significant

Figure no. 22

The resources and information of narcotics and its addiction is yet limited for the young adults. There are very limited community who provide awareness and information regarding addiction and narcotics. In our study out of 959 young adult 926 i.e 96.6% students believe that there should be more support group and resources specially for young adult students struggling with narcotics.

Table no. 22: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Have You Ever Participated in Any Narcotic Addiction Prevention or Awareness Programs?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	65	7.3%
No	889	92.7%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=935.87 df=18 p value, sig=0.0129, significant

Figure no. 23

Out of 959 young adult 889 i.e 92.7% students were attending narcotics addiction awareness programs for the first time. The problems of narcotics misuse is a major issue in our community

although the solution to improve knowledge and awareness of narcotics is yet to be come in focus for the students.

Table no. 23: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

Have You Ever Participated In A Peer Support Group For Those Recovering From Narcotic Addictions?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	67	7%
No	886	92.4%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=885.48 df=14 p value, sig=0.0132, significant

Figure no. 24

Most of the young adult students were not join in peer support group in their life. In our study out of 959 students 886 i.e 92.4% students were not ever

join or participate in any kind of peer support group in their life

Table no. 24: Pre & Post Questionnaire comparison

How Effective Do You Think These Programs Are At Increasing Awareness And Preventing Narcotic Addiction?	Frequency In Number	Percentage (%)
More	881	91.9%
Less	47	4.9%
Intermediate	31	3.2%
Total	959	100%

χ^2 value=794.44 df=10 p value, sig=0.0183, significant

Figure no. 25

Although regarding narcotics the students were accepting this kind of program for the first time in their life but most of the young adult i.e 881(91.9%) out of 959 students feel this kind of

program can increase awareness more effectively in the prevention of addiction of narcotics.

I. CONCLUSION

In the pursuit of unravelling the dynamics of narcotics awareness among young adults, this study has provided invaluable insights into the demographic nuances, the impact of awareness programs, and the prevailing attitudes and concerns within this demographic. As we conclude this exploration, several key findings emerge, shedding light on both the successes achieved and the challenges that lie ahead in the realm of narcotics education and prevention. The study underscores the vulnerability of young adults, particularly males, to narcotics introduction. The higher representation of males (65.1%) signals a crucial area for targeted interventions and educational programs tailored to address gender-specific risk factors. Understanding these demographic nuances is essential for tailoring prevention strategies that resonate with the specific challenges faced by different groups within the young adult population. The age distribution analysis reveals a significant disparity in awareness levels across different age groups. While the 22-23 age group exhibited the highest awareness (39.9%), the 18-19 age group lagged behind at 11.2%. This calls for focused efforts in education and prevention strategies tailored to bridge this critical gap. Targeting awareness initiatives toward specific age brackets ensures that interventions are timely and resonate with the evolving needs of the young adult demographic. The post-program surge in awareness from 7.6% to 97.7% signifies a remarkable achievement. Educational initiatives have proven to be highly effective in disseminating information about narcotics, resulting in a substantial increase in knowledge across key aspects such as risk, addiction, and signs/symptoms. The positive change in participants' confidence regarding information about narcotics (93.4%) further

underscores the transformative impact of these programs. The study reveals a notable belief among participants (89.6%) that their colleges lack adequate information about narcotics. This highlights a critical gap in institutional preparedness, emphasizing the need for comprehensive substance abuse education within college curricula. Collaborative efforts between educational institutions and health authorities are crucial to ensuring a well-informed student body and fostering an environment that actively addresses narcotics-related challenges. The positive shift in concerns about narcotics risks (from 90.9% to 85.4%) and the perception of narcotics as a minor community problem (from 92.7% to 85.8%) post-program indicate a change in attitudes. Participants are showing greater empowerment and preparedness to address the challenges posed by narcotics, reflecting the influence of increased awareness and education. This attitudinal shift is pivotal for community mobilization and concerted efforts to tackle narcotics as a major public health concern. The acknowledgment of peer pressure as a significant cause of narcotics misuse, coupled with the increase in confidence in resisting peer pressure (from 93% to 85%), highlights the role of awareness programs in empowering individuals to make informed and independent choices. The substantial increase in knowledge about where to seek help for narcotics issues (from 6.2% to 96.8%) addresses a crucial aspect of combating substance misuse by ensuring that individuals are aware of available support resources. The heightened concern for the current opioid crisis (92.7%) post-program indicates a broader awareness of the societal implications of narcotics misuse. This heightened awareness is pivotal for fostering a sense of collective responsibility and mobilizing efforts to address the multifaceted challenges posed by narcotics. The high attendance (92.9%) at the first narcotics education

program signals a willingness among participants to actively engage with educational initiatives. The perception among participants (89.5%) that there are insufficient resources for those struggling with narcotics highlights a critical area for intervention. Efforts to enhance resources, support networks, and treatment options should be prioritized to create a more robust infrastructure for individuals facing substance misuse challenges. While there is a noticeable gap between attendance at narcotics education programs (92.7%) and participation in peer support groups (92.4%), the positive perception (91.9%) of the potential effectiveness of peer support groups in increasing awareness indicates a willingness among participants to explore collaborative initiatives. Integrating peer support programs into broader community interventions could enhance their impact on awareness and prevention. The implications of our findings are profound, carrying significance for multiple stakeholders. At the forefront are young adults themselves. The nuanced understanding of their awareness patterns can empower them to make informed decisions about narcotics. Armed with knowledge about the risks and consequences, they can navigate the complexities of a world where narcotics are readily accessible and often glamorized. Our findings indicate that tailored

REFERENCES

1. Rogers AJ. Narcotic Addiction Among Young People. *Fed. Probation*;1970;34:34.
2. Arria A. M., Caldeira K. M., Bugbee B. A., Vincent K. B., & O'Grady, K. E.; The academic and social profile of college students on ADHD medication who misuse their medication. *Journal of Attention Disorders*. 2015; 19(11):940-948.
3. Zhuravleva LA. Factors and conditions of the spread of narcotics among young people. *Russian Education & Society*. 2001 Nov 1;43(11):19-28.
4. Adrian M. A critical perspective on cross-cultural contexts for addiction and multiculturalism: Their meanings and implications in the substance use field. *Substance use & misuse*. 2002 Jan 1;37(8-10):853-900.
5. Kolodny A, Courtwright DT, Hwang CS, Kreiner P, Eadie JL, Clark TW, Alexander GC. The prescription opioid and heroin crisis: a public health
6. Joseph H, Appel P. Historical Perspectives and. State methadone treatment guidelines. 1993;1:11.

educational programs targeting different segments of young adults, considering their age, educational level, and experiences, are crucial to addressing knowledge gaps and enhancing awareness. Educational institutions, from schools to universities, play a pivotal role in narcotics awareness. By incorporating evidence-based educational programs into the curriculum, they can foster a generation of young adults who are equipped to make informed decisions about narcotics. Furthermore, healthcare professionals must be prepared to provide accurate information and support to those in need. Early intervention and access to resources are essential to preventing narcotics misuse and addiction. In understanding narcotics awareness among young adults, we found a significant increase in knowledge and positive shifts in attitudes post-awareness programs. However, challenges remain, particularly in addressing gender and age-specific vulnerabilities. Collaborative efforts between institutions and ongoing awareness campaigns are vital to sustaining positive changes and fostering a supportive environment for those at risk. Prioritizing resources, combating stigma, and integrating peer support can contribute to a comprehensive approach in preventing narcotics misuse among young adults.

7. Hendricks G, Savahl S, Florence M. Adolescent peer pressure, leisure boredom, and substance use in low-income Cape Town communities. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*. 2015 Feb 7;43(1):99-109.
8. Escobedo A. A brief history of drugs: From the stone age to the stoned age. Simon and Schuster; 1999 May 1.
9. Eddy NB. The history of the development of narcotics. *Law and Contemporary Problems*. 1957 Jan 1;22(1):3-8.
10. Davenport-Hines R, Davenport-Hines RP. The pursuit of oblivion: A global history of narcotics. WW Norton & Company; 2003 Nov 10.
11. Martel M. The Pursuit of Oblivion. A Global History of Narcotics Richard Davenport-Hines. *Canadian Bulletin of Medical History*. 2007 Apr;24(1):213-4.
12. Buxton J. The historical foundations of the narcotic drug control regime. World Bank Publications; 2008.
13. Hanes WT, Sanello F. The opium wars: the addiction of one empire and the corruption of another. Sourcebooks, Inc.; 2002.
14. Buchanan WW, Rainsford KD, Kean CA, Kean WF. Narcotic analgesics. *Inflammopharmacology*. 2023 Jul 29;1-6.
15. Chaves C, Remiao F, Cisternino S, Declèves X. Opioids and the blood-brain barrier: a dynamic interaction with consequences on drug disposition in brain. *Current neuropharmacology*. 2017 Nov 1;15(8):1156-73.
16. Clausen JA. Early history of narcotics use and narcotics legislation in the United States. *InDrugs and Politics* 2017 Jul 12 (pp. 23-29). Routledge.
17. Goodman J, Sherratt A, Lovejoy PE, editors. Consuming habits: drugs in history and anthropology. Routledge; 2014 Apr 8.
18. Voss HL, Stephens RC. Criminal history of narcotic addicts. InDrug Forum 1973. Baywood Publishing Company.
19. Hser YI, Anglin MD, Powers K. A 24-year follow-up of California narcotics addicts. *Archives of general psychiatry*. 1993 Jul 1;50(7):577-84.
20. Fortuna RJ, Robbins BW, Caiola E, Joynt M, Halterman JS. Prescribing of controlled medications to adolescents and young adults in the United States. *Pediatrics*. 2010 Dec 1;126(6):1108-16.
21. Hudgins JD, Porter JJ, Monuteaux MC, Bourgeois FT. Prescription opioid use and misuse among adolescents and young adults in the United States: A national survey study. *PLoS medicine*. 2019 Nov 5;16(11):e1002922.
22. Martinotti G, Lupi M, Carlucci L, Cinosi E, Santacroce R, Acciavatti T, Chillemi E, Bonifaci L, Janiri L, Di Giannantonio M. Novel psychoactive substances: use and knowledge among adolescents and young adults in urban and rural areas. *Human Psychopharmacology: Clinical and Experimental*. 2015 Jul;30(4):295-301.
23. Bykov SA. Narcotics abuse among young people as an indicator of dysadaptation. *Russian Education & Society*. 2001 Nov 1;43(11):46-56.
24. Daniulaityte R, Falck R, Carlson RG. Sources of pharmaceutical opioids for non-medical use among young adults. *Journal of psychoactive drugs*. 2014 May 27;46(3):198-207.
25. Das NP, Ratty AK. Studies on the effects of the narcotic alkaloids, cocaine, morphine, and codeine on nonenzymatic lipid peroxidation in rat brain mitochondria. *Biochemical medicine and metabolic biology*. 1987 Apr 1;37(2):258-64.

26. Molinari SP, Cooper JR, Czechowicz DJ. Federal regulation of clinical practice in narcotic addiction treatment: purpose, status, and alternatives. *Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics*. 1994;22(3):231-9.
27. Deschenes EP, Anglin MD, Speckart G. Narcotics addiction: Related criminal careers, social and economic costs. *Journal of Drug Issues*. 1991 Apr;21(2):383-411.
28. Bloodworth D. Opioids in the treatment of chronic pain: legal framework and therapeutic indications and limitations. *Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Clinics*. 2006 May 1;17(2):355-79.
29. Kushner HI. Historical perspectives of addiction. *Addiction Medicine: Science and Practice*. 2011:75-93.
30. Hargreaves K, Abbott PV. Drugs for pain management in dentistry. *Australian dental journal*. 2005 Dec;50:S14-22.
31. Manning P, editor. *Drugs and popular culture*. Routledge; 2013 Jan 11.
32. Hickman TA. Drugs and race in American culture: Orientalism in the turn-of-the-century discourse of narcotic addiction. *American Studies*. 2000 Apr 1;41(1):71-91.
33. approach to an epidemic of addiction. *Annual review of public health*. 2015 Mar 18;36:559-74.
34. Hawk KF, Vaca FE, D'Onofrio G. Focus: Addiction: Reducing fatal opioid overdose: Prevention, treatment and harm reduction strategies. *The Yale journal of biology and medicine*. 2015 Sep;88(3):235.
35. Sindelar JL, Fiellin DA. Innovations in treatment for drug abuse: Solutions to a public health problem. *Annual Review of Public Health*. 2001 May;22(1):249-72.
36. Gerstein DR, Green LW. Preventing drug abuse. *What Do We Know?*. 1993.
37. Fortuna RJ, Robbins BW, Caiola E, Joynt M, Halterman JS. Prescribing of controlled medications to adolescents and young adults in the United States. *Pediatrics*. 2010 Dec 1;126(6):1108-16.
38. Mojtabai R, Olfson M, Han B. National trends in the prevalence and treatment of depression in adolescents and young adults. *Pediatrics*. 2016 Dec 1;138(6).
39. Wren AA, Bensen R, Sceats L, Dehghan M, Yu H, Wong JJ, MacIsaac D, Sellers ZM, Kin C, Park KT. Starting young: trends in opioid therapy among US adolescents and young adults with inflammatory bowel disease in the Truven MarketScan database between 2007 and 2015. *Inflammatory bowel diseases*. 2018 Sep 15;24(10):2093-103.
40. Sung HE, Richter L, Vaughan R, Johnson PB, Thom B. Nonmedical use of prescription opioids among teenagers in the United States: Trends and correlates. *Journal of Adolescent Health*. 2005 Jul 1;37(1):44-51.
41. Brown R. A., Abrantes A. M., Minami H., Prince M. A., Bloom E. L., Apodaca T. R., et.al; Motivational interviewing to reduce substance use in college students: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*. 2014; 82(3):417-428.
42. Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality. *National Survey on Drug Use and Health: Detailed Tables*. Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration. 2019.
43. Pilkington H. Beyond 'peer pressure': Rethinking drug use and 'youth culture'. *International Journal of Drug Policy*. 2007 May 1;18(3):213-24.
44. Hansen WB, Graham JW. Preventing alcohol, marijuana, and cigarette use among adolescents: Peer pressure resistance training versus establishing conservative norms. *Preventive medicine*. 1991 May 1;20(3):414-30.

45. Costello M, Thompson S. Preventing opioid misuse and potential abuse: the nurse's role in patient education. *Pain Management Nursing*. 2015 Aug 1;16(4):515-9.
46. Denisco RC, Kenna GA, O'Neil MG, Kulich RJ, Moore PA, Kane WT, Mehta NR, Hersh EV, Katz NP. Prevention of prescription opioid abuse: the role of the dentist. *The Journal of the American Dental Association*. 2011 Jul 1;142(7):800-10.
47. Manworren RC, Gilson AM. Nurses' Role in Preventing Prescription Opioid Divers. *The American Journal of Nursing*. 2015 Aug 1;115(8):34-40.
48. Bobo LD, Thompson V. Unfair by design: The war on drugs, race, and the legitimacy of the criminal justice system. *Social Research: An International Quarterly*. 2006;73(2):445-72.
49. Dorn N, South N. Drug markets and law enforcement. *The British Journal of Criminology*. 1990 Mar 1;30(2):171-88.
50. Sitorus RJ. Use of narcotics supports risk behaviors. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan Masyarakat*. 2016 Feb 21;7(1):58000.
51. Sinha R. Chronic stress, drug use, and vulnerability to addiction. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 2008 Oct;1141(1):105-30.
52. White WL. The mobilization of community resources to support long-term addiction recovery. *Journal of substance abuse treatment*. 2009 Mar 1;36(2):146-58.
53. Richert T., Anderberg M, Dahlberg M. Mental health problems among young people in substance abuse treatment in Sweden. *Substance abuse treatment, prevention, and policy*. 2020 Dec;15(1):1-10.
54. Levy S., Youth and the opioid epidemic. *Pediatrics*. 2019 Feb 1;143(2).
55. Uhl G.R, Koob GF, Cable J. The neurobiology of addiction. *Annals of the New York academy of sciences*. 2019 Sep;1451(1):5-28.
56. Spencer M.R, Weathers S. Trends and risk factors of adolescent opioid abuse/misuse: understanding the opioid epidemic among adolescents. *International Journal of Adolescent Medicine and Health*. 2020 May 12;33(4):2349-3429.
57. Lyons R.M, Yule AM, Schiff D, Bagley SM, Wilens TE. Risk factors for drug overdose in young people: a systematic literature. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2019 Aug 1;29(7):487-497.
58. Putri M, Damaiyanti S. Description of former characteristics of drug users (narcotics, alcohols, psychotropics and other addictives) post rehabilitation of the national narcotics agency in the city and district of solok. *InProceeding International Conference Syedza Saintika* 2020 Oct 19; 1(01):355-490.
59. Ivanich JD, Weckstein J, Nestadt PS, Cwik MF, Walls M, Haroz EE, O'Keefe VM, Goklish N, Barlow A. Suicide and the opioid overdose crisis among American Indian and Alaska Natives: a storm on two fronts demanding swift action. *The American journal of drug and alcohol abuse*. 2021 Sep 3;47(5):527-34.
60. Ignaszewski MJ. The epidemiology of drug abuse. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 2021 Aug;61:10-17.
61. Krebs E., Min JE, Zhou H, Davison C, McGowan G, Nosyk B. The cascade of care for opioid use disorder among youth in British Columbia, 2018. *Journal of Substance Abuse Treatment*. 2021 Nov 1;130:108-404.
62. Bagley SM, Laroche MR, Xuan Z, Wang N, Patel A, Bernson D, Silverstein M, Hadland SE, Land T, Samet JH, Walley AY. Characteristics and receipt of medication treatment among young adults who

- experience a nonfatal opioid-related overdose. *Annals of emergency medicine*. 2020 Jan 1;75(1):29-38.
63. Fishman M., Wenzel K, Scodes J, Pavlicova M, Lee JD, Rotrosen J, Nunes E. Young adults have worse outcomes than older adults: Secondary analysis of a medication trial for opioid use disorder. *Journal of Adolescent Health*. 2020 Dec 1;67(6):778-85.
64. Wren AA, Bensen R, Sceats L, Dehghan M, Yu H, Wong JJ, MacIsaac D, Sellers ZM, Kin C, Park KT. Starting young: trends in opioid therapy among US adolescents and young adults with inflammatory bowel disease in the Truven MarketScan database betstudyen 2007 and 2015. *Inflammatory bowel diseases*. 2018 Sep 15;24(10):2093-103.
65. Bennett KG, Harbaugh CM, Hu HM, Vercler CJ, Buchman SR, Brummett CM, Waljee JF. Persistent opioid use among children, adolescents, and young adults after common cleft operations. *The Journal of craniofacial surgery*. 2018 Oct;29(7):1697.
66. Laksana AW. Sociological Analysis of Narcotics Circulation Treatment on Students. *Jurnal Pembaharuan Hukum*. 2021 Apr 15;8(1):105-17.
67. Schoenberger SF, Park TW, dellaBitta V, Hadland SE, Bagley SM. "My life Isn't defined by substance Use": Recovery perspectives among young adults with substance Use disorder. *Journal of general internal medicine*. 2022 Mar;37(4):816-22.
68. Betts AC, Murphy CC, Shay LA, Balasubramanian BA, Markham C, Allicock M. Polypharmacy and prescription medication use in a population-based sample of adolescent and young adult cancer survivors. *Journal of Cancer Survivorship*. 2023 Aug;17(4):1149-60.
69. Hudgins JD, Porter JJ, Monuteaux MC, Bourgeois FT. Prescription opioid use and misuse among adolescents and young adults in the United States: A national survey study. *PLoS medicine*. 2019 Nov 5;16(11):e1002922.
70. Wheeler M, Merten JW, Gordon BT, Hamadi H. CBD (cannabidiol) product attitudes, knowledge, and use among young adults. *Substance use & misuse*. 2020 Apr 15;55(7):1138-45.
71. Dumbili EW, Gardner J, Degge HM, Hanewinkel R. Enhancement motivations for using prescription drugs among young adults in Nigeria. *International Journal of Drug Policy*. 2021 Sep 1;95:102995.
72. Lankenau SE, Schragger SM, Silva K, Kecojevic A, Bloom JJ, Wong C, Iverson E. Misuse of prescription and illicit drugs among high-risk young adults in Los Angeles and New York. *Journal of public health research*. 2012 Mar;1(1):jphr-2012.
73. Chua KP, Brummett CM, Conti RM, Bohnert A. Association of opioid prescribing patterns with prescription opioid overdose in adolescents and young adults. *JAMA pediatrics*. 2020 Feb 1;174(2):141-8.
74. Grutman AJ, Stewart C, Able C, Agrawal P, Galansky L, Gabrielson A, Haney N, Kohn TP, Crigger CB. Postoperative Opioid Prescribing in Adolescents and Young Adults After Urologic Procedures Is Associated With New Persistent Opioid Use Disorder: A Large Claims Database Analysis. *Urology*. 2023 Sep 9.
75. Rifiana AJ, Afrizal A, Machmud R, Edwin A, Mallongi A. Development of Family-Based Narcotics Abuse Model Rehabilitation among Adolescents with EVIE Method in DKI Jakarta in 2017-2019. *Open Access Macedonian Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2020 Aug 10;8(E):4348.
76. Kuźnicki P, Neubauer K. Emerging comorbidities in inflammatory bowel disease:

- eating disorders, alcohol and narcotics misuse. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2021 Oct 8;10(19):4623.
77. Bollom JE, Baldé A, Jandi Z, Boiro H, Einarsdóttir J, Gunnlaugsson G. Social determinants of narcotics use susceptibility among school-attending adolescents in Bissau, Guinea-Bissau: a cross-sectional analysis. *Adolescents*. 2021 Aug 3;1(3):306-20.
78. Stanley LR, Crabtree MA, Swaim RC. Opioid misuse among American Indian adolescents. *American journal of public health*. 2021 Mar;111(3):471-4.
79. Gushgari AJ, Driver EM, Steele JC, Halden RU. Tracking narcotics consumption at a Southwestern US university campus by wastewater-based epidemiology. *Journal of hazardous materials*. 2018 Oct 5;359:437-44.
80. Ariyanti V. The victims of drugs abuse and their legal status in the Indonesian narcotics law. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*. 2017;13(4):119-23.
81. Chen YC, Lee CY, Chen SJ. Narcotic addiction in failed back surgery syndrome. *Cell transplantation*. 2019 Mar;28(3):239-47.
82. Akhgari M, Amini-Shirazi N, Irvani FS. Forensic toxicology perspectives of methadone-associated deaths in Tehran, Iran, a 7-year overview. *Basic & clinical pharmacology & toxicology*. 2018 Apr;122(4):436-41.
83. Joudrey PJ, Edelman EJ, Wang EA. Methadone for opioid use disorder—decades of effectiveness but still miles away in the US. *JAMA psychiatry*. 2020 Nov 1;77(11):1105-6.
84. Khantzian, E.J., 1974. Opiate addiction: A critique of theory and some implications for treatment. *American Journal of Psychotherapy*, 28(1), pp.59-70.
85. Lord S, Brevard J, Budman S. Connecting to young adults: an online social network survey of beliefs and attitudes associated with prescription opioid misuse among college students. *Substance use & misuse*. 2011 Jan 1;46(1):66-76.
86. Martinotti G, Lupi M, Carlucci L, Cinosi E, Santacroce R, Acciavatti T, Chillemi E, Bonifaci L, Janiri L, Di Giannantonio M. Novel psychoactive substances: use and knowledge among adolescents and young adults in urban and rural areas. *Human Psychopharmacology: Clinical and Experimental*. 2015 Jul;30(4):295-301.
87. Eisenberg D., Gollust S. E., Golberstein E., & Hefner J. L.; Prevalence and correlates of depression, anxiety, and suicidality among university students. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*. 2007; 77(4):534-542.
88. Palamar J. J., Shearston J. A., Cleland C. M., & Weitzman M.; Powder cocaine and crack use in the United States: An examination of risk for arrest and socioeconomic disparities in use. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*. 2015; 149:108-116

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